

Synthesis of Substituted Anilic Acid Hydrazides and their Hydrazones as Possible Antimicrobial Agents

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In a search for new antimicrobial agents, substituted anilic acid hydrazides and their different acid hydrazones have been synthesised. All the acid hydrazides and some of the acid hydrazones were tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity with encouraging results.

ISONICOTINIC acid hydrazide¹ (INH) and its *N'*-isopropyl derivative are effective drugs in the treatment of human tuberculosis. Although tuberculostatic activity has been shown by some other pyridine and non-pyridine hydrazides, but none is found superior to isonicotinic acid hydrazide. Different condensation products of a number of hydrazides with various aldehydes and ketones were also examined² with a view for reducing the toxicity due to free amino group. Hydrazones have also been found to possess antibacterial^{3,4}, antifungal⁵ as well as insecticidal activity^{6,7}. In this laboratory also a number of acid hydrazides and acid hydrazones have been prepared^{8,9}.

The present work deals with the condensation of different substituted aromatic aldehydes and ketones with three (bromo-substituted) malon-anilic acid hydrazides. The condensation took place readily in alcoholic medium and 25 new acid hydrazones were prepared. All the acid hydrazides and some acid hydrazones synthesised have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Experimental

Melting points recorded are uncorrected.

Malon-4-bromo-2-methyl anilic acid hydrazide : A mixture of 4-bromo-2-methyl aniline (18.6 g) and freshly distilled diethyl malonate (24 g) was refluxed to gentle ebullition for 1 h. After cooling ethanol (50 ml) was added. The crystals of dianilides which separated out were filtered and the filtrate was concentrated over a water-bath. This solution was treated with 99% hydrazine hydrate (5 ml) and stirred well. The mixture was set aside for 2 h, and the solid separated was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, yield (5.2 g, 68%), m.p. 198° (Found: C, 41.50; H, 4.20; N, 14.86; Br, 28.27. C₁₀H₁₀O₂N₂Br requires: C, 41.96; H, 4.22; N, 14.68; Br, 27.95%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 660, 698 (C—Br), 1 620, 1 670 (CONH), 1 416, 1 462 (COCH₂CO),

3 250 (NH₂), 3 010 (CCH₃), 1 538 and, 1 579 cm⁻¹ (aromatic character).

Malon-4-bromo-2-methylanilic acid hydrazone of salicylaldehyde : Malon-4-bromo-2-methylanilic acid hydrazide (0.57 g) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) and salicylaldehyde (0.21 g) was refluxed for 0.5 h. White crystals obtained on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol, (0.73 g, 93%) m.p. 238° (Found: C, 52.60; H, 3.96; N, 10.50; Br, 20.03. C₁₇H₁₆O₃N₂Br requires: C, 52.30; H, 4.10; N, 10.76; Br, 20.50%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 650 (C—Br), 1 598 (CONH), 1 662 (CONHN=C), 3 190 (COCH₃), 1 378 (COCH₂CO), 2 900 (CCH₃), 1 280, 1 350 (C—OH in aromatic ring), 922 and 1 022 cm⁻¹ (1,2,4-substitution in benzene ring).

By adopting the above procedure the new acid hydrazides and acid hydrazones were obtained and their analytical data, m.p. and yields are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

TABLE 1—M.p. AND Yield of Compound

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	CH ₃	H	Br	198	68
2.	H	OH ₂	Br	191	78
3.	Br	H	OH ₂	176	84

Antibacterial and antifungal activity test : All the acid hydrazides and some acid hydrazones were screened for their antibacterial as well as antifungal activity *in vitro*. The results are summarised in Table 3.

TABLE 2—M.P. AND YIELD OF COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no.	R	X	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %
4.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄ .	H	CH ₃	H	Br	238	93
5.	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	H	Br	232	83
6.	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	H	Br	218	47
7.	5-NO ₂ .2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	CH ₃	H	Br	237	84
8.	5-Cl.2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	CH ₃	H	Br	227	67
9.	3,4-di-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	CH ₃	H	Br	250	77
10.	2-OH.C ₁₀ H ₇	H	CH ₃	H	Br	239	66
11.	3,5-di-I.2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	CH ₃	H	Br	188	58
12.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	H	OH ₃	Br	228	86
13.	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	OH ₃	Br	218	91
14.	CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₅	—	H	OH ₃	Br	231	91
15.	3,5-di-Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	H	CH ₃	Br	223	72
16.	2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	H	H	CH ₃	Br	200	63
17.	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	H	CH ₃	Br	219	73
18.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	H	CH ₃	Br	241	92
19.	5-Cl.2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	H	CH ₃	Br	223	86
20.	5-NO ₂ .2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	Br	H	CH ₃	209	65
21.	2-OH.C ₁₀ H ₇	H	Br	H	CH ₃	220	74
22.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	Br	H	CH ₃	203	67
23.	3,4-di-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	Br	H	CH ₃	237	82
24.	3,5-di-Cl.2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	Br	H	CH ₃	222	53
25.	3,5-di-Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	Br	H	CH ₃	200	65
26.	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	Br	H	CH ₃	189	83
27.	OH ₃ .C ₆ H ₅	—	Br	H	CH ₃	223	63
23.	5-Cl-3-NO ₂ .2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	Br	H	CH ₃	182	85

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and halogen analyses.

TABLE 3—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY (τ/ml) OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.*	<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	<i>K. leb</i>
1	12.5	—	—
2	1.56	—	—
3	12.5	—	25
7	—	50	—
14	—	—	25
18	3.12	—	—
24	100	—	—
25	—	100	—
28	—	100	—

* The number corresponds to that of Sl. no. in Tables 1 and 2.

References

1. H. H. FOX, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 542.
2. NG. PH. BUU-HOI, NG. D. XUONG, NG. H. NAM, F. BINON and R. ROYER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1358.
3. R. H. WILLEY and R. L. CLAVENGER, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, 5, 1367 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, 58, 12508).
4. J. SUPNIEWSKI, T. BENY and J. KRUPINSKA, *Bull. Acad. Pol. Sci.*, 1955, 3, 55 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, 50, 7800).
5. A. MARGOT and H. GYSIN, U. S. Pat., 2 740 762/1956 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, 50, 10770, 12122).
6. W. R. ADDER and D. P. WRIGHT, U. S. Pat., 3 157 569/1962 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 62, 3976).
7. G. T. BOTTGER, A. P. YERINGTON and S. I. GERTLER, U. S. Deptt. Agr. Bur. Entomol and Plant Quarantine, 1951, E-815, p. 17 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1952, 46, 5778).
8. B. S. RATHORE and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 591.
9. O. P. SINGHAL and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 479.

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